

WAYS TO IMPROVE PROFESSIONAL ETHICS IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY.

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Annotation: Formation of professional ethics of a preschool teacher educational institution begins with the formation of moral personality traits of the teacher himself, goes through a path of long-term development, as in the process of independent practical activity of the teacher, personal life experience and in the process of advanced training. Professional ethics of a preschool teacher to a large extent determined not only by the level of his pedagogical training, but also desire for self-improvement in a professional environment activities. The problem of ethical behavior of preschool teachers arises from from the real needs of updating the preschool education system. The task of professional ethics of teachers is the introduction of moral the fundamentals of forming a teacher's personality in everyday activities

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Main part: Ethics is a humanitarian doctrine of morality, its basis is concept of good and evil. The goal of ethics is a model of humane and fair relationships that provide quality communication for more high level. The main question of ethics: identifying the reasons for right and wrong correct behavior of society. Morality and morality are that fine line of social ideas of an individual person about the concept of good and evil, about the correctness of the actions taken. Morals and ethics represent a set of norms, attitudes, values that filter human behavior and are the most important foundations of culture generally. Morality is not a theoretical system, but a practical ideal. Morality is what takes a person out of the animal state and raises to "divine" heights. The emergence of ethics occurred more than two and a half thousand years ago. Initially it was considered as an important part of philosophy. Ethics originally denoted the habitual place of living together. Subsequently, ethics began to mean custom, a person's disposition, and his character. One of the fragments of Heraclitus says that a person's "ethos" is his deity. In science, ethics is understood as a field of knowledge, and morality or morality is what it studies. In living language this distinction is not yet available. The term "ethics" is sometimes also used to designate a system of moral and ethical standards of a certain kind. social group.

Teaching plays an important role in the development of society. One of the key issues of today is the formation of pedagogical behavior in future teaching. It is a difficult process for a teacher to integrate into the student environment. However, her teaching activities are conducted directly among students. Strengthening relationships with feelings of trust and friendship requires serious psychological training from the teacher. In order to do so, the teacher should immediately respond to the changing pedagogical situations in the classroom, consisting of students of different character. In pedagogy, one of the most important traits of morality and ethics is defined as the desire of the individual to maintain a stable, close relationship with those around him. This aspiration ensures that the teacher is able to communicate quickly with students and those around them and achieve the stated goal. Psychologists argue that the teacher's sympathetic nature is characterized by two categories of people: First, extraverted persons: active, serious and restrained in all affairs, prone to calmness and external influence. The second is the introvert individuals: those who are exclusively focused on their own inner world, who do not interfere with their surroundings, who are prone to self-control, reflexion, and constant anxiety. Once de Balzac says, "courtesy and modesty are proof that a person is truly educated." English man John Libbock says that "through carelessness, people can achieve victories that cannot be achieved by force." YG Jacobson, author of several works on professional ethics, describes: "Professional ethics is a set of ethical norms, concepts, evaluations and ideals that are characteristic of a particular profession in a given society." Professional ethnocentrists point out in their writings that professional ethics is

inextricably linked to human ethics. Diversity in the level of development of the moral consciousness of different professions is maintained in the context of society. At present, there are ethical requirements for people of different professions. The problem of human formation is extremely complex and multifaceted. Some aspects of this problem are being investigated more effectively in modern pedagogical science: - researches on such problems as perspective model of education, directed to pedagogical process, relatively ideal condition of professional, moral formation. Because, to a certain extent, students' behavior is defined, their existing levels of personal qualities that are defined and their intended ideal level is improved; - Creation of effective systems, forms, methods of education; developing a system of knowledge selection and measures are necessary to achieve a specific goal; - Psycho-pedagogical study of the characteristics of the formation of the necessary qualities, qualities that are required for the formation of a fully developed personality; - Creation of an effective system of control over the educational process and monitoring of the educational process. The teaching profession is, in essence, moral, and therefore, the teacher himself must have a well-rounded outlook and an example of personal conduct. In the professional culture of future teachers, the following will play an important role: - pedagogical requirements; - axiological factors; - modern needs. Professional competence in pedagogical requirements, professional skills in axiological factors, and professional qualifications in the modern requirements are the primary basis. All of these constitute the requirements for the professional culture of future teachers. When it comes to the requirements for the professional culture of future teachers, it is worth mentioning the following requirements set by the thinker Alisher Navoi (1441 -1501) in the book "Mahbub ul – kulub": "...the teacher knows the subject he is teaching and loves his students; ...be demanding for himself and his pupil; ...respect for society; Teaching learners what they already know; ...should be free of social and spiritual defects." Also, the formation of students' pedagogical ethics should be the basis of the educational process. Organization of professional and ethical education gives students the active life-style of the teacher, the ability to master good manners. For effective organization of professional and moral education: - accurately describe, justify the ideal of professional and moral formation; - Determine the current level of professional and moral formation in the morning; In our view, it is desirable to analyze the related concepts in two dimensions in forming the qualities of pedagogical ethics as part of moral education: the first is the attitude of the society towards the teacher; the second is the attitude of the teacher to the community. The relationship of a person to a person is part of the second group relationship. They will be partially covered in the course of professional education. The foregoing requires that the formation of pedagogical ethics be a separate area of education. This is especially important for the education system of pedagogical institutions, as the teaching profession is at the heart of the teaching profession. This, in turn, requires a clear definition of what the content of a profession-oriented education should look like. Because the educational process should be aimed at developing future teachers' ethical behavior and the results of the learning process should be compared with the ideal.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it is worth noting that students and future teachers will be exploring ways to develop self-ethical and pedagogical behavior.

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